

1 **Amelioration of pulmonary immune activation to support ventilation through alveolar regeneration:**
2 **CCL4.**

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7 Chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPD) include the condition emphysema wherein the alveoli in
8 the lung which contract and expand to conduct gas exchange are damaged and the sufferer experiences
9 limited ventilation (breathing) (1-3). Tissue damage and pathology resulting from immune activation is a
10 theme in pulmonary biology (4-6). We measured total transcription in the lungs of humans with COPD
11 and in healthy control individuals to identify immune activation-associated factors that contribute to
12 disease pathology and tissue damage in emphysema (7). We identified the C-C motif chemokine ligand
13 *CCL4* among the gene products whose expression was most significantly up-regulated and differentially
14 expressed transcriptome-wide in the lungs of humans with COPD. *CCL4* was transcriptionally
15 co-regulated with the pro-inflammatory cytokines tumor necrosis factor (TNF) and interleukin-1 β in the
16 human lung. Targeting and neutralization of *CCL4* is a viable therapeutic strategy to limit immune
17 pathology and support enhanced ventilation through regeneration of the alveoli in humans with a leading
18 cause of mortality, emphysema.
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We studied whole transcription in the human lung, in health and in humans with the chronic obstructive pulmonary disease emphysema, to understand the molecular mechanisms underlying tissue damage and pathology in COPD.

Figure 1: CCL4 is produced in large quantities in the lungs of patients with emphysema.

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$n=19$ lung tissue from $n=6$ individuals (control)

$n=37$ lung tissue from $n=11$ humans with COPD (emphysema)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
6351	1.33e-16	0.2388	-8.271024	-1.9753888	193.13	CCL4	56/15183	99.6

Next, we utilized a next-generation systems biological method (8) to understand the function of CCL4 in the lung by querying multiple tissue settings to identify its transcriptionally co-regulated gene partners.

Figure 2: Expression of CCL4 in the lung is associated with transcription of TNF and IL-1 β .

1 In the human lung, CCL4 was transcriptionally co-regulated with the pro-inflammatory cytokines
2 TNF and IL-1 β , as well as the chemokines CXCL9 and CXCL10.

3 4 **Discussion**

5 We identified here CCL4 as a central component of the gene signature of human emphysema, a
6 leading cause of death in humans.

7 **References**

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